
**Deliverable D-JRP-
PARADISE-WP3.2**
**Report on the identification
of markers for multi-locus
sequence typing of
Cryptosporidium parvum
and *Giardia duodenalis***

**Workpackage 3 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE**

Responsible Partners: P27-ISS, P11-
RKI, P41-SVA, P23-UoS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2
Project Acronym	JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE
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Other contributors	PARADISE consortium
Due month of the report	M42
Actual submission month	M45
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: September 1 st , 2021
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s): European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites, National EU Reference Laboratories for Parasites</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2

REPORT ON THE IDENTIFICATION OF MARKERS FOR MULTI-LOCUS SEQUENCE TYPING OF *CRYPTOSPORIDIUM PARVUM* AND *GIARDIA DUODENALIS*

**This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation**

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP3 Design, implementation and validation of MLST schemes

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP3-T2 Development of MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

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1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain.

The objectives of PARADISE WP3 are:

- To select new markers *in silico* for robust high resolution genotyping of *C. parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* using whole genome data generated in WP2-T1, unpublished data from within the consortium and publically available data
- To develop multilocus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*
- To conduct an inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes

The procedures undertaken for *in silico* detection of variable regions suitable for subsequent selection of markers for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* to address are described in deliverable:

Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1 Report on the *in silico* selection of highly polymorphic sequences in *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* genomes

<https://zenodo.org/record/4452772>

This deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2 reports on work carried out to address the second objective of PARADISE WP3, namely development of MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*, and includes a plan for future work towards this objective.

2. *Cryptosporidium parvum*

2.1 Novel MLST markers

Primers were designed to amplify highly polymorphic regions in the *C. parvum* genome which were identified as described in D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1. A total of 28 primer pairs, 18 designed at SVA and 10 designed at ISS, were then tested in the laboratory. Primers were initially tested at SVA and ISS on DNA extracted from purified *C. parvum* oocysts and products were submitted for Sanger sequencing in both directions. Eighteen primer pairs were subsequently tested on five DNA samples extracted from *C. parvum*-positive faecal samples containing different oocyst concentrations based on a *C. parvum* specific qPCR. Table 1 summarises the results for each primer pair. Overall, 21 primer pairs showed strong and consistent amplification of a single band with no non-specific amplification. Clean, interpretable Sanger sequences were obtained from the PCR products amplified by these primers.

Table 1. Summary of characteristics and performance of 28 primer pairs designed for typing of *C. parvum* by MLST

Marker	Chromosome	PCR product size (bp)	Amplification of DNA from purified <i>C. parvum</i>	Amplification of DNA from <i>C. parvum</i> -positive faecal samples
1 (CPATCC_0035770)	1	489	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 38.21)*
2 (CPATCC_0035880)	1	535	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 35.51)
3 (CPATCC_0039030)	1	469	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.3)
4 (CPATCC_0028230)	2	498	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.06)
5 (CPATCC_0029910)	2	576	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 35.51)
6 (CPATCC_0031960)	3	595	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.3)
7 (CPATCC_0035350)	3	493	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 35.51)
8 (CPATCC_0018920)	4	442	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 35.51)
9 (CPATCC_0021750)	4	509	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.3)

10 (CPATCC_0024650)	5	536	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 38.21)
11 (CPATCC_0011480)	6	568	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 38.21)
12 (CPATCC_0011530)	6	514	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 38.21)
13 (CPATCC_0012400)	6	512	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.3)
14 (CPATCC_0007000)	7	568	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 38.21)
15 (CPATCC_0010930)	7	600	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.06)
16 (CPATCC_0001010)	8	560	Yes/Yes	Yes (Cq – 33.06)
17 (CPATCC_0001650)	8	439	Yes/ Weak, multiple bands	Yes (Cq – 33.3)
18 (CPATCC_0002930)	8	564	Yes/ Weak, multiple bands	Yes (Cq – 38.21)
21 (CP1051)	4	618	Yes/Yes	N/D
22 (CP611)	2	678	Yes/No	N/D
23 (CP907)	3	655	Yes/Yes	N/D
24 (CP1516)	6	430	Yes/Yes, weak	N/D
25 (CP686)	3	362	Not distinct/No	N/D
26 (CP318)	2	261	Yes/Yes	N/D
27 (CP1860)	6	242	Yes/Yes	N/D
28 (CP2089)	7	346	Not distinct/No	N/D
29 (CP2337)	8	475	Yes/Yes	N/D
30 (CP1495)	5	539	Yes/Yes	N/D

Abbreviations: Fw = forward sequence, Rv = reverse sequence, - = no readable sequence generated, double = double peaks, mc = ?, N/D = not determined; * Cq = the sample with the highest Cq (from a *C. parvum* specific qPCR) that can be amplified by the primer pair.

To investigate the utility of the markers amplified by the primer sets in distinguishing between *C. parvum* isolates, and to narrow down the number of markers for further testing, an *in silico* approach was undertaken. Nineteen markers were selected based on good results in initial laboratory testing and coverage of the eight *C. parvum* chromosomes. Whole genome sequence data (either publicly available or generated as part of PARADISE WP2) from 137 *C. parvum* isolates from human and animals in 13 European countries were interrogated to obtain sequences at each marker locus. Sequences for each locus were aligned, SNPs were identified and the number of different genotypes at each locus was determined. Ultimately, each isolate was assigned a 19-digit code indicating which genotype was found at each locus. Using all 19 markers, it was possible to distinguish between most isolates except for 6 sets (generally pairs) of isolates from the same country, which may represent outbreaks/shared infection origin. Analysis is ongoing to reduce the number of markers to eight while ensuring coverage of all chromosomes and maintaining the level of discrimination between isolates.

Table 2. *In silico* discrimination of *C. parvum* isolates using 19 MLST markers

Country	Number of isolates analysed	Number of unique genotypes	Number of shared genotypes
United Kingdom	29	29	0
Italy	27	26	1
Finland	17	13	1
Germany	16	16	0
Hungary	11	8	1
Denmark	9	8	1
France	7	7	0
Slovenia	6	6	0
Sweden	5	4	1
Norway	4	4	0
Poland	2	2	0
Portugal	1	1	0

China	1	1	0
Egypt	1	1	0

2.2. VNTR markers

As an alternative approach to *C. parvum* typing, seven unpublished variable number tandem repeat (VNTR) markers, developed at the *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit (CRU) in the UK (CRU is an associate partner of the Paradise project, Responsible Dr. Rachel M. Chalmers) were tested on DNA extracted from 48 *C. parvum* positive faecal samples from humans in the Netherlands and cattle in Sweden and the Netherlands. All samples were successfully amplified at the seven marker loci and PCR products were submitted for fragment size analysis. Fragment sizes were determined using Genemapper and translated into single and multilocus genotype codes. The matrix of multilocus genotypes was then used to infer the clustering of isolates. As depicted in Figure 1, human- and ruminant-derived parasite isolates formed two separated clusters, although a few human-derived isolates appear to cluster closely with ruminant-derived isolates.

Figure 1. Principal component analysis. Clustering of *C. parvum* isolates (n=48), based on fragment sizes of seven VNTR markers. Human-derived isolates are shown in orange and cattle-derived isolates in blue.

3. *Giardia duodenalis*

3.1 Assemblage B markers

Of the 42 highly polymorphic regions in the *G. duodenalis* assemblage B genome identified in WP3 task 1 (as described in D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1), 20 were selected and nested primer sets were designed to amplify the regions. In initial testing, the 40 selected primer pairs amplified PCR products of expected sizes using genomic DNA from 5 different assemblage B isolates (from axenic cultures) as templates. Bidirectional Sanger sequencing of nested PCR products confirmed expected sequences. In further testing on DNA from 10 *Giardia* assemblage B-positive cyst/faecal samples, 8 out of the 10 samples could be amplified by the primers. Sequences for each isolate at each marker locus were aligned and SNPs were identified. Table 3 summarises the results for each nested primer set.

Table 3. Summary of characteristics and performance of 20 primer pairs designed for typing of *G. duodenalis* assemblage B by MLST

Marker	Chromo-some localization (based on WB6 reference)	Outer PCR product size (bp)	Nested PCR product size (bp)	PCR positive samples (N=13)	Mean ambiguities per isolate	Mean SNPs per isolate	No. of polymorphic sites in consensus
1	1	578	538	13	3.2	15	50
2*	4	593	553	13	3.9	13	43
3	2	700	657	13	6.4	20	79
4	5	573	533	13	2.6	8	32
7*	3	577	562	13	3.2	12	49
8*	2	570	529	12	5.5	15	50
9	3	689	650	11	3.5	13	36
10*	5	598	557	12	6.5	18	56
11	4	629	582	12	4.5	15	43
13	5	661	622	8	3.8	16	37
14*	1	536	498	10	3.1	12	37
15	5	802	762	12	5.7	19	65
16	2	793	752	12	4	19	47
17	4	697	654	11	6.7	19	66
18	5	634	593	11	6.4	19	75
19	5	547	506	12	2.9	10	26
20*	5	656	616	13	3	15	42
21	5	551	512	11	2.2	8	28
22	3	565	523	9	2.3	10	29
27	1	543	503	10	2.3	7	17

* Markers selected for further testing.

Six markers (indicated with asterisks in Table 3), were tentatively selected for further testing based on the following criteria: coverage of all chromosomes, positivity rate of PCR and Sanger sequencing, number of polymorphic sites, avoidance of intergenic regions and sequence length.

An issue identified in the analysis of sequences from the 20 marker loci, which as previously been demonstrated for other markers used to type *G. duodenalis* assemblage B (Woschke et al., 2021), is the presence of “double peaks” in sequencing chromatograms, likely due to allelic sequence heterozygosity (ASH), which is common in assemblage B and complicates the interpretation of typing data. This is represented by “mean ambiguities per isolate” in Table 3. However, in line with the objectives of the work that focuses on the suitability of the new typing scheme for reliable analysis of isolates for epidemiological purposes such as outbreak investigation, the identified markers revealed higher potential discriminatory power than current typing markers. They will be therefore further pursued for establishment of a new typing scheme.

3.2 Assemblage A markers

The availability within the consortium of *G. duodenalis* assemblage A samples from different countries and hosts has provided an opportunity to further test a published MLST scheme involving six markers for assemblage A (Ankarklev et al. 2018). Twenty samples from humans in Italy (including samples from an outbreak), nine samples from humans in Germany and nine samples from cattle in Poland were typed using the MLST scheme as described (Ankarklev et al. 2018). The resulting data were combined with published (Ankarklev et al. 2018, Woschke et al. 2021), and unpublished data (ISS). The resolution of the scheme will be assessed by cluster analyses. A publication describing the results is planned.

Next steps

- Select 8 *C. parvum* MLST markers for further testing
- Confirm selection of 6 *G. duodenalis* assemblage B MLST markers
- Conduct laboratory testing of the selected markers on a panel of *C. parvum*, *G. duodenalis* assemblage B samples from humans and animals available at ISS, RKI SVA and UoS (see Table 4) to confirm amplification and determine ability to discriminate between parasite strains
- Develop MLST protocols for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* assemblage B
- Share protocols with PARADISE consortium members for further sample testing
- Conduct an analysis of the population structure of *C. parvum* and of *G. duodenalis* across Europe using the MLST data generated
- Complete analysis of *G. duodenalis* assemblage A typing

Table 4. Samples available for MLST marker testing

Parasite	Source	Country	Sample number
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Humans/environment/cattle	Hungary	50
	Humans/animals	Italy	50
	Animals	Latvia	29 Cp; 9 other
	Humans	Netherlands	26 Cp; 49 Ch
	Cattle	Poland	29 Cp; 20 other
	Cattle	Portugal	8
	Humans/animals	Sweden	100
	Human/animals	UK	86 Cp; 10 Ch; 4 other
	Cattle/buffalo	USA	50 Cp
<i>Giardia</i>	Humans/environment	Hungary	51
	Humans/animals	Italy	50
	Cattle/pigs	Poland	37 Ass A, B; 4 Ass E
	Animals	Portugal	6
	Humans/animals	UK	100 Ass A, B
	Human	Travellers returning to Germany)	200 Ass A, B
	Humans/environment	Hungary	51

This activity is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

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